

On the effect of probe tube presence on measured hearing aid transmission behavior

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Abstract

It is well-known in hearing aid related real-ear measurements that placement of a probe tube may lead to leakage effects that change the outcomes. However, quantitative data on the issue are rare and inconclusive, and it has not been assessed how the effects differ between coupling styles. We present measurements of the probe tube presence effect (PTPE) in four different earmold styles and three different types of generic domes in fourteen ears, covering all relevant metrics of acoustic coupling. The data show that the PTPE that is, on average across ears, measurable in all conditions, but most critical when the coupling is occluded and the length of the sealing zone is short, as in specific earmold types and power domes.

1 Introduction

Measurement of hearing aid behavior in the real ear of a user is recommended by many best-practice guidelines for hearing aid fitting [1, 2, 3]. To this end, silicone tubes with a typical outer diameter of 1–1.5 mm are placed in the ear together with the hearing aid earpiece. The probe tube conducts sound from an inlet positioned close to the eardrum to a microphone body located outside the ear [4]. Such measurements allow to verify and adjust hearing aid output to the individual ear acoustics. Similar measurements are also applied, although less routinely, to assess the transmission behavior of headphones or earphones [5, 6].

Probe tubes are typically placed between the earpiece and the ear canal walls, which can introduce an additional leak that is not present during daily use. This may lead to differences in hearing aid transmission behavior between normal use and probe tube measurements, hereafter referred to as the Probe Tube Presence Effect (PTPE). Due to this leak, the low-frequency response of the hearing aid driver may be reduced, while the leakage of external sounds and the feedback path may increase. It is well recognized that the PTPE may occur during probe tube measurements [7, 8, 4], especially with closed fittings. Several studies have assessed potential measurement errors caused by probe tube placement—specifically the position of the probe tube opening in the ear canal—due to the complex acoustics of the ear canal [9, 10]. However, only a few quantitative assessments of the acoustic effects of an additional leak have been conducted [11, 8], and no conclusive data on the magnitude and relevance of the PTPE as a function of hearing aid coupling are available.

In the present work, we evaluated the PTPE across a range of hearing aid couplings, including four different earmold designs and three types of domes with varying intended venting of the ear canal. We assessed differences in the hearing aid driver response at the eardrum, the attenuation of external sounds, and the feedback path resulting from the insertion of a probe tube between the earpiece and the ear canal. For earmolds, acoustic measurement data for the condition without such a probe tube were obtained using a probe tube routed through an additional matched bore within the earmold. As this procedure was not considered feasible for domes, the PTPE for the driver response at the eardrum was additionally assessed using threshold measurements, with the hearing aid driver serving as the sound source. Measurements were conducted in one ear of each of fourteen young adult participants.

2 Methods

2.1 Participants and Earpieces

Fourteen normal-hearing volunteers aged between 29 and 48 years (mean: 36.2; 7 males and 7 females) participated in the study. Prior to the experiments, otoscopic examination confirmed the absence of excessive cerumen accumulation and of any external ear conditions that could interfere with the measurements. All experiments were conducted by a trained hearing care professional. Participants received financial compensation for their

Figure 1: A-D: Design view of earmolds in one participant, with beige bodies showing the resulting earmolds and the yellow shade denoting the ear canal geometry as captured by a digitized ear impression. E-G: Images of the domes utilized (right).

participation and provided written informed consent. Ethical approval for the study was granted by Technische Hochschule Lübeck (approval date: 2020-09-11).

Figure 1 shows the earmolds and domes used in the present study. Four earmold types and three dome types were evaluated in each subject. The earmolds were manufactured by a laboratory based on individual ear impression scans obtained approximately six months prior to the study. Domes were available in four sizes and were selected individually for each participant by the experimenter.

The four earmold types included a standard closed ring-style design (Closed Earmold, A), the same design with a 2 mm vent (Vented Earmold, B), a "nugget" earmold (C), and a plug-style silicone earmold (D). While earmolds A–C were made of hard acrylic material, earmold D was made of soft silicone (approximately 45 Shore). In addition to the vent, all earmolds included a separate bore for the probe tube (see below). Earmolds A and B were identical except for the vent and extended a few millimeters beyond the first bend of the ear canal. The nugget earmold (C) is a specialized design intended to reduce the occlusion effect and is characterized by deep insertion into the second bend of the ear canal. Sealing is achieved only within a 4–5 mm zone at the tip, while material is largely removed from the lower and anterior parts of the external ear canal. A cymba-style hook provides retention in the ear. No vent is included in this design. The silicone earmold (D) follows a plug-style design and extends approximately as deep as the nugget earmold. Insertion of the receiver is facilitated by a matched rubber ring bonded into the earmolds. All earmolds were ordered from a laboratory offering these designs as standard options.

The domes were standard styles, including open (E), tulip (F), and power (G) domes distributed for use with Widex hearing aids, which showed good compatibility with the receiver used (see below).

2.2 Experimental Setup

Figure 2 shows the measurement setup in the ear. A behind-the-ear with receiver-in-canal (BTE-RIC) style hearing aid dummy with wired microphones and receiver (earpieces of Portable Hearing Lab, Bat&Cat Sound Labs, Palo Alto, USA) was coupled to the right ear of each participant. The wired transducers enabled the reproduction of arbitrary signals through the hearing aid receiver and the measurement of microphone input

Figure 2: Sketch of measurement setup in the ear.

signals for transfer function analysis. Participants were seated in a sound-treated booth, directly facing a coaxial loudspeaker (Genelec 8351A, Iisalmi, Finland) at a distance of 1 m. For loudspeaker calibration, a free-field microphone (Bruel&Kjaer 4190, Virum, Denmark) was placed at the position of the participant’s head in the absence of the participant.

All transducers were connected to a sound card (Fireface 802, RME, Haimhausen, Germany) via appropriate amplifiers and power supplies. Measurements were controlled using custom routines implemented in MATLAB R2024b.

Two probe tube microphones (ER7C, Etymotic Research, Elk Grove Village, USA) were used to measure the sound pressure at the eardrum. One of them, referred to as the reference probe tube microphone, was used only in measurements involving earmolds and was inserted into the ear canal through a dedicated canal integrated into the earmold. The inner diameter of this canal was matched to the outer diameter of the probe tube (1.3 mm), such that insertion of the reference probe tube was assumed not to introduce additional leakage. The second probe tube microphone, referred to as the measurement probe tube microphone, was placed between the earpiece and the ear canal, entering the ear canal at the notch between the tragus and anti-tragus, following clinical practice. The insertion depth was controlled by visual inspection to approximately 3 mm from the eardrum in the open ear, and marked accordingly. It was assumed that this distance from the eardrum did not introduce errors due to standing waves in the frequency range of interest, primarily below 1 kHz.

2.3 Procedure and Metrics

Two independent sets of measurements were conducted: transfer function measurements and audiogram measurements. Transfer function measurements comprised the determination of transfer functions from the hearing aid receiver voltage u_{ha} and the loudspeaker (referenced to the level at the free-field microphone p_{ff}) to the sound pressure at all microphone locations: the hearing aid microphone p_{ha} , the reference probe tube microphone $p_{ed}^{(ref)}$, and the measurement probe tube microphone $p_{ed}^{(meas)}$. Transfer functions were obtained using the exponential sweep technique [12], which allows interleaving measurements from both sources to reduce measurement time [13]. The sweeps from each source had a duration of 10 s, covered a frequency range from 50 Hz to the Nyquist frequency of 22,050 Hz, and were presented at levels of 75 dB SPL (loudspeaker) and 11.2 mV (hearing aid receiver), yielding comparable free-field equivalent sound pressure levels at the eardrum.

The following transfer functions were evaluated in detail for both the reference and measurement conditions:

- The hearing aid driver response

$$H_{ha} = 20 \log_{10} \left| \frac{p_{ed}}{u_{ha}} \right|, \quad (1)$$

which depends on both the individual ear canal volume and the acoustic impedance of the earpiece.

- The Real-Ear Occluded Insertion Gain

$$\text{REOIG} = 20 \log_{10} \left| \frac{p_{ed}^{(occl)}}{p_{ff}} \right| - 20 \log_{10} \left| \frac{p_{ed}^{(open)}}{p_{ff}} \right|, \quad (2)$$

where the superscripts (occl) and (open) denote measurements in the occluded and unaided ear, respectively, both obtained using the reference microphone. Note that the first term in Eq. 2 is commonly referred to as the Real-Ear Occluded Gain (REOG), and the second term as the Real-Ear Unaided Gain (REUG). The REOIG quantifies the attenuation of external sounds due to the presence of the hearing aid earpiece and thus characterizes the tightness of fit.

- In addition, the feedback path

$$H_{fb} = 20 \log_{10} \left| \frac{p_{ha}}{u_{ha}} \right| \quad (3)$$

was assessed but is not further analyzed in this study, as it did not provide additional relevant information beyond the other metrics. The results are, however, provided in the original data.

Audiogram measurements consisted of determining the hearing threshold for pure-tone stimulation via the hearing aid receiver, recording the corresponding receiver voltage at threshold T . Thresholds were determined by manual adjustment following clinical practice, using a step size of 1 dB at audiometric frequencies between 125 Hz and 2 kHz.

Both measurement types were conducted for three insertions of each earpiece under two conditions: (1) a reference condition, with only the reference probe tube microphone in place for earmolds and no probe tube for domes, and (2) a measurement condition, with the measurement probe tube microphone additionally inserted. Probe tube microphones were left in place during reinsertions. The order of reference and measurement conditions was alternated across insertions, and the order of earpieces was balanced across subjects using a randomized Latin square design. Measurements were distributed across two sessions of approximately two hours each, during which three or four earpieces were tested per session.

Based on the coupling conditions described above, the influence of the measurement probe tube was quantified as the difference between the reference and measurement conditions. These difference metrics were defined as

- Hearing aid response difference

$$\Delta H_{ha} = H_{ha}^{(meas)} - H_{ha}^{(ref)} \quad (4)$$

- REOIG difference

$$\Delta \text{REOIG} = \text{REOIG}^{(meas)} - \text{REOIG}^{(ref)} \quad (5)$$

- Threshold difference

$$\Delta T = T^{(ref)} - T^{(meas)} \quad (6)$$

Note that the difference metrics are defined such that their values represent level changes at the eardrum caused by the insertion of the measurement probe tube.

Figure 3: Simplified equivalent circuit model of hearing aid driver coupled to the ear canal, valid for frequencies below approx. 1 kHz.

2.4 Equivalent Circuit Modeling

The results were further evaluated in terms of equivalent circuit model parameters in order to obtain more generalizable outcomes. For frequencies below approximately 1 kHz, the hearing aid driver coupled to the ear canal can be modeled using an equivalent circuit, as shown in Figure 3. Here, the driver is represented as an ideal volume velocity source with known source flux q_s [14]. In this low-frequency regime, the ear canal and the coupled middle ear can be reasonably approximated by an acoustic compliance determined by the enclosed volume V_{ec} . The coupling is represented by an acoustic mass M_{cp} , which may describe a vent, small leakages between the earpiece and the ear canal, or vibrations of the earpiece due to incoming sound. If a probe tube is present, an additional parallel acoustic mass M_{lk} represents the leakage created by slits between the probe tube, the ear canal walls, and the earpiece. Note that this simplified model does not include resistive components present in the ear canal; however, their influence can be neglected for the extracted metrics described below.

The pressure at the eardrum in this model is given by

$$p_{ed} = q_s Z_{tot}, \quad (7)$$

with the total impedance Z_{tot} given by

$$Z_{tot} = \frac{1}{\frac{1}{i\omega M_c} + i\omega V_{ec}} \quad (8)$$

and the combined acoustic mass

$$M_c = \frac{M_{lk} M_{cp}}{M_{lk} + M_{cp}}. \quad (9)$$

At frequencies as low as 100 Hz, Z_{tot} is dominated by the acoustic mass even for critical combinations of large ear canal and middle ear volumes and high acoustic impedance up to approximately 50,000 $\frac{\text{kg}}{\text{m}^4}$ [15, 16]. Hence, in this low-frequency limit, the second term in the denominator of Z_{tot} can be neglected, and Eq. (7) simplifies to

$$p_{ed} = q_s i\omega M_c. \quad (10)$$

Thus, if q_s is known, the acoustic mass of the coupling can be estimated from measured data as

$$\hat{M}_c = \text{imag} \left(\frac{p_{ed}(f_r)}{2\pi f_r q_s(f_r)} \right). \quad (11)$$

To enable estimates in all conditions, including the reference case with domes where no direct measurement of p_{ed} was available, threshold measurements at $f_r = 125$ Hz were used, and the appropriate p_{ed} at threshold calculated. estimate the individual level at threshold, the driver voltage at threshold in the measurement condition was inserted into the corresponding H_{ha} , and the resulting level averaged across the three insertions. Since no variations larger than ± 1.5 dB were observed across participants, this estimate was considered reliable. In Eq. (11), this individual threshold level was substituted for p_{ed} in all conditions, and q_s was adjusted according to the driver voltage at threshold for each condition. A reference frequency f_r of 125 Hz was chosen as the lowest frequency at which a sufficient signal-to-noise ratio was achieved in all relevant measurements, while still ensuring dominance of the acoustic mass in Z_{tot} .

In the reference case, the combined impedance equals the coupling impedance,

$$\hat{M}_{cp} = \hat{M}_c. \quad (12)$$

In the measurement case, the estimated \hat{M}_c contains contributions from both \hat{M}_{cp} and \hat{M}_{lk} . The leakage mass \hat{M}_{lk} can be estimated by rearranging Eq. (9) as

$$\hat{M}_{lk}^{(m,r)} = \frac{\hat{M}_c^{(m)} \hat{M}_{cp}^{(r)}}{\hat{M}_{cp}^{(r)} - \hat{M}_c^{(m)}}, \quad (13)$$

where m and r denote repetitions in the measurement and reference conditions, respectively. Since \hat{M}_c and \hat{M}_{cp} cannot be determined independently, a total of nine estimates of \hat{M}_{lk} result from the three repetitions of each quantity. This estimation becomes numerically ill-conditioned when \hat{M}_c and \hat{M}_{cp} are similar in magnitude, and results in such cases should be interpreted with caution. Instances where \hat{M}_c was equal to or larger than \hat{M}_{cp} were excluded from the numerical evaluation, as they would yield non-physical negative or infinite values. However, their occurrence was recorded. In these cases, the coupling appeared more occluded in the measurement condition than in the reference condition, suggesting that variability in M_{cp} may exceed that of M_{lk} . It should also be noted that, due to the 1 dB quantization of threshold measurements and a resulting minimum difference of M_{cp} and M_{lk} , maximum values of \hat{M}_{lk} are bounded to $8.2 \hat{M}_{cp}$. For threshold differences of 2 dB and 3 dB, the ratios $\hat{M}_{lk}/\hat{M}_{cp}$ are 3.9 and 2.4, respectively.

Figure 4: Coupling parameters for all earpieces. Each row shows a metric as denoted by the y-label (see Methods for details), each column shows the result for one appropriate coupling as denoted in the column title. Thin colored lines indicate individual results obtained in the measurement case (subject number given in legend), thick solid and dashed lines indicate averages across participants in the measurement and reference cases, respectively. Note that the reference case is not available in the domes.

As a metric independent of individual data, the general effect of a leakage on the pressure generated by the hearing aid driver at low frequencies can be considered. Since the compliance term is negligible in this regime, the pressure ratio resulting from the introduction of M_{lk} can be approximated as

$$\Delta p_{ed} = \frac{p_{ed}^{(tot)}}{p_{ed}^{(cp)}} \approx \frac{M_{lk}}{M_{lk} + M_{cp}}. \quad (14)$$

3 Results and Analysis

3.1 Coupling analysis

Figure 4 shows the raw coupling data for all conditions. The rows display the hearing aid driver response H_{ha} , the REOIG, and the driver voltage at threshold T , while the columns represent the different couplings. The couplings differ primarily in their degree of occlusion: a more closed coupling is characterized by a higher level of H_{ha} at low frequencies below 1 kHz, lower REOIG values in the frequency range up to 2 kHz, and lower driver voltages at threshold. The closed and nugget earmolds achieved the most occluding coupling, whereas the open dome exhibited the least attenuation. Whenever differences between the measurement and reference conditions are apparent (solid and dashed lines, respectively), all metrics consistently indicate reduced sealing in the measurement condition. Note that the reference condition for H_{ha} and REOIG is only available for the earmold measurements.

Across all metrics, a considerable amount of both inter- and intra-individual variability is observed. Without attempting to explicitly quantify or disentangle these sources of variability, it is worth noting that measurements were generally repeatable within participants, as indicated by thin lines of the same color often lying close together in Fig. 4. Variability in the measured transfer functions (H_{ha} and REOIG) is lower and typically does not exceed ± 5 dB in cases where sealing effects are negligible, for example in the open dome and for H_{ha} between 1 and 4 kHz. The highest variability is observed for the power dome, reaching a range of up to 30 dB across individual measurements.

3.2 Measured Probe Tube Presence Effects

Figure 5 shows the PTPE observed for the different metrics. Note that for the domes, the PTPE can only be expressed in terms of threshold differences, as reference measurements for H_{ha} and REOIG are not available. All individual combinations of reference and measurement conditions are shown, i.e., up to 9 curves per participant,

Figure 5: PTPE for all earpieces and obtained metrics. Each row shows a metric as denoted by the legend (see Methods for details), each column shows the result for one appropriate earpiece as denoted in the column title. All other details per Figure 4

along with the average across participants, following the same visualization style as in Fig. 4. For H_{ha} and REOIG, the displayed level differences, including their sign, directly reflect the effect of probe tube presence. For the hearing threshold, the PTPE is expressed as the equivalent effect on H_{ha} .

For H_{ha} , the PTPE appears as a level reduction at frequencies below 1 kHz, most prominently for the nugget earmold, with an average reduction of approximately -10 dB at 100 Hz. In the closed and silicone earmolds, average reductions of about 5 dB at 100 Hz are observed. While the PTPE manifests as a high-pass-like effect in these three earmolds, it appears as a mild dip in the vented earmold, with a maximum reduction of about 2 dB around 500 Hz. The PTPE observed in the threshold differences largely mirrors the results for H_{ha} . It can therefore be expected that similar reductions occur for H_{ha} in the dome conditions. Whereas the PTPE does not exceed an average of 2 dB for the open and tulip domes, the power dome shows results comparable to the nugget earmold, representing another condition with a potentially large PTPE.

For the REOIG, the PTPE manifests as a level increase, i.e., an increase in the sound pressure level leaking into the ear canal, across a broad frequency range. This effect peaks at approximately 7 dB, 5 dB, and 4 dB for the closed, nugget, and silicone earmolds, respectively. In the vented earmold, the PTPE is only apparent above 1 kHz and reaches a maximum of about 5 dB at 6 kHz. Based on the comparison of threshold and REOIG results for the earmolds, it is not expected that larger REOIG differences than those observed for the vented earmold will occur for the open and tulip domes. However, for the power dome, a REOIG difference due to the PTPE comparable in magnitude to that of the nugget earmold may be expected.

Again, substantial inter- and intra-individual variability is observed, with overall ranges of 20–30 dB in many metrics. As in the coupling analysis, the results are well repeatable within many participants, as indicated by thin lines of the same color in Fig. 5.

3.3 Probe Tube Presence Effects Expressed as Acoustic Mass

Figure 6 shows the acoustic masses of the coupling and the leakage, extracted using Eqs. (9)–(13), providing a more generalizable representation of the results. The degree of sealing described in Fig. 4 is well reflected by the extracted acoustic masses: the highest acoustic masses in the reference conditions are observed for the closed and nugget earmolds, with median values across participants of approximately $20,000$ kg/m⁴, whereas the lowest acoustic mass, around 400 kg/m⁴, is found for the open dome. For most couplings, the modeled leakage masses are, on median, approximately 2–4 times larger than the corresponding acoustic masses in the reference condition.

As noted in the Methods section, the estimation of \hat{M}_{lk} is bounded and quantized due to the quantization of threshold differences. This effect is clearly visible when comparing the extracted leakage masses for the closed and vented earmolds: although a difference in \hat{M}_{lk} is observed, such a difference would not necessarily be expected given that the outer geometry of the earmolds is identical. The proportion of ill-conditioned cases—likely associated with higher true values of \hat{M}_{lk} for each coupling—is indicated in Fig. 6. However, in

Figure 6: Acoustic masses estimated from the experiment. Symbols show median across participants and insertions, whiskers toe 5 and 95% percentiles. The bo on top shows the percentage of instances where the computation of acoustic mass of the probe tube leakage was ill-conditioned.

Figure 7: Background color shows the level reduction due to probe tube presence as approximated by eq. (14), depending on the acoustic mass of the coupling M_{cp} and leakage due to probe tube presence M_{lk} . Extracted results for couplings as per Fig. 6 are printed on top, with symbols and errorbars indicating the median and 90% confidence intervals, respectively.

cases where a substantial difference between reference and measurement conditions is evident, the estimated leakage mass can be considered reliable.

Consistent with the previous metrics, the most pronounced effects of probe tube leakage are observed for the nugget earmold and the power dome. For the nugget earmold, the median leakage mass is lower than the acoustic mass in the reference condition, resulting in a substantially reduced overall acoustic mass in the measurement condition. A similar pattern is observed for the power dome, where the acoustic masses of the reference coupling and the leakage are of comparable magnitude, also leading to a marked reduction in the overall acoustic mass in the measurement condition.

Finally, Figure 7 visualizes the general effect of leakage on H_{ha} as a function of the coupling and the magnitude of the leakage. This is shown as a color map based on Eq. (14), with the extracted acoustic masses of the couplings overlaid. The plot clearly illustrates that critical PTPE values occur for combinations of high coupling masses and low leakage masses, located in the lower right region of the diagram.

Most couplings (open and tulip domes; closed, vented, and silicone earmolds) fall within the green region of the plot, indicating that the PTPE is close to negligible. These data points are arranged around a diagonal line that approximately represents $M_{lk} = 3M_{cp}$, which corresponds to an upper bound in the experimental estimation of M_{lk} . As in the previous analyses, the most critical effects are observed for the nugget earmold and the power dome. For these couplings, the median values lie within the orange to red regions of the

diagram, indicating potential low-frequency reductions in H_{ha} of up to approximately 10 dB, consistent with the observations in Fig. 5.

4 Discussion

4.1 Probe tube presence effects across hearing aid couplings

The present data show that a PTPE is, on average across participants, observable in most participants and couplings. That is, the presence of a probe tube introduces additional leakage, which leads to a reduced acoustic output of the hearing aid driver at low frequencies and decreased attenuation of external sounds. The reduction in hearing aid output was measured both directly at constant driving voltage and indirectly by determining the driving voltage at hearing threshold.

It is evident from both qualitative inspection of the results (Fig. 5) and equivalent circuit modeling (Figs. 6 and 7) that the magnitude of the PTPE varies across couplings. Specifically, the PTPE depends on the combination of the original acoustic mass of the coupling and the acoustic mass of the leakage introduced by the probe tube. It is important to note that the geometry of the coupling influences not only its own acoustic mass but also the acoustic mass of probe-tube-induced leakage paths. The acoustic mass of vents or leakages is proportional to their length and inversely proportional to their cross-sectional area [17, 18]. For a significant PTPE to occur, the acoustic mass of the leakage must be comparable to or smaller than that of the coupling itself. This condition is met when the probe tube creates a relatively short and wide leakage path while no comparable venting is already present.

In the domes, probe tubes can easily create relatively large leakage paths due to deformation of the silicone flanges. These leakage paths are also relatively short due to the geometry of the domes. In the open and tulip domes, the already low acoustic mass of the coupling prevents the occurrence of a significant PTPE. However, in the power dome, a potentially critical PTPE arises from the combination of high acoustic sealing and low acoustic mass of the probe-tube-induced leakage. It can be expected that existing datasets describing the acoustics of domes [19] are biased the PTPE, both in terms of a systematic offset and increased variability. These data may therefore not fully represent real-use acoustics, particularly for more occluding dome designs.

In the earmolds, only a small PTPE was observed for the occluded earmold. Although this coupling exhibited the highest acoustic mass among all conditions, a large PTPE was likely avoided due to the comparatively large length of the earmold, which results in a high acoustic mass of the probe-tube-induced leakage. A similar observation applies to the silicone earmold. This design did not include venting but showed a lower acoustic mass, presumably due to a less controlled fit of the plug-style design without structural support in the pinna. It should be noted that the PTPE may increase if earmolds provide a tighter and more consistent seal, as suggested by the present data. The results do not indicate that probe-tube-induced leakage is less pronounced for softer earmold materials.

For the vented earmold, a similar acoustic mass of the probe-tube-induced leakage as in the occluded earmold can be assumed. However, the presence of the vent reduces the PTPE and shifts the frequency range in which it is observed. The most critical design overall is the nugget earmold. In this case, the short sealing region within the second bend of the ear canal results in an acoustic coupling mass comparable to that of the occluded earmold. However, the probe tube introduces a leakage path of much shorter length and thus lower acoustic mass, leading to a pronounced PTPE.

4.2 Relevance of PTPE for hearing aid fitting

When hearing aid gain is adjusted using real-ear measurements, the most critical consequence of the PTPE is the apparent reduction in hearing aid output. If a significant PTPE is present, the reduced output level may be overcompensated, leading to excessive amplification at low frequencies once the probe tube is removed and the original acoustic seal is restored. The PTPEs observed for H_{ha} in this study would directly translate into erroneous level increases due to measurement errors, which can reach up to approximately 20 dB (see Fig. 5) in some participants and coupling conditions.

Caution is also warranted when using automated real-ear measurements or other acoustic tests integrated into modern hearing aid fitting software. Even if low-frequency gain adjustments are manually corrected following automated procedures, measurements obtained under falsely open coupling conditions may have more subtle effects on processing parameters. For example, maximum gains may be overly restricted due to an underestimation of feedback stability, or high-pass characteristics of the output, used to mitigate comb-filtering effects [20], may be tuned too aggressively.

For practical applications, PTPEs below approximately 5 dB are likely small enough to be negligible, given the inherent variability of audiometry, perceptual detection thresholds for gain adjustments [21], and best-practice accuracy targets for real-ear-based hearing aid fitting. PTPEs exceeding this threshold can be expected in power domes, nugget earmolds, or similar coupling designs that occlude the ear canal using a short sealing

zone. In other coupling types, PTPEs are typically negligible compared to the existing uncertainty of real-ear measurements. It should be emphasized that, due to substantial inter-individual variability, applying generic corrections, either globally or for specific earpiece types, does not appear feasible.

A suitable strategy for handling PTPE in practice is to avoid relying uncritically on real-ear measurements at low frequencies in cases with potentially critical couplings and instead to use estimated values during manual adjustment. For earmolds, the PTPE can be effectively mitigated by incorporating a dedicated bore that allows the probe tube to be guided without introducing additional leakage. This bore can be sealed during daily use. Based on the present data, this approach is particularly recommended for designs with narrow sealing zones, which are more susceptible to probe-tube-induced leakage.

For domes, guiding the probe tube through a dedicated opening remains largely experimental and carries the risk of altering the coupling characteristics in unintended ways. During the preparation of the present study, several attempts were made to implement this approach; however, satisfactory results were not achieved, particularly for the double-flanged power dome. Guiding probe tubes through domes is more feasible for single-flanged designs, although its practical applicability in clinical settings remains questionable. When real-ear measurements are performed with occluding domes, longer designs with a more anatomical shape should be preferred in order to minimize the PTPE.

4.3 Variation of probe tube presence effect between and within subjects

The PTPE showed large variations both between and within participants, with good repeatability within most participants. It is worth noting that the largest variability was observed in designs where the PTPE is most relevant. For example, in the nugget earmold, many ears show a PTPE in H_{ha} at 125 Hz of around 0 dB, whereas for other ears a repeatable PTPE of up to 20 dB was observed. This indicates that the PTPE is likely influenced by individual anatomical features, such as ear canal shape, earmold fit, and skin properties. Within individual participants, results were largely repeatable. However, it should be noted that the probe tube was not removed and reinserted between measurements, which could represent an additional source of within-subject variability that was minimized in the present study. Future studies could also assess the influence of probe tube positioning on the PTPE.

The variability of the PTPE across participants also raises concerns regarding its dependence on specific patient groups. While, for practical reasons, the current cohort covered a broad adult age range, many typical hearing aid users are either older or younger. In particular, in pediatric hearing care, real-ear measurements (e.g., of the Real-Ear-to-Coupler Difference) are recommended due to ear canals that significantly deviate in size from standard couplers [8]. Due to generally smaller ear canals and typically less compliant skin, it can be hypothesized that PTPEs may be more pronounced in pediatric hearing aid fitting than in other patient groups. Future studies should therefore evaluate these effects and their potential implications in pediatric hearing care. To reiterate, especially for this vulnerable group, the present data suggest guiding the probe tube through a dedicated bore in the earmold that is occluded after measurements.

5 Conclusion

The present study provides a comprehensive dataset characterizing the effect of leakage due to the presence of a probe tube on hearing aid transmission parameters. Such leakage is present during real-ear measurements but not during daily use and may therefore lead to inaccurate hearing aid fitting. These leakages can be described by a parallel acoustic mass and thus have effects equivalent to those of an additional vent. Probe tube presence effects therefore result in reduced attenuation of external sounds and decreased low-frequency output of the hearing aid driver, which may lead to over-amplification and other suboptimal hearing aid settings. While PTPEs were observable in all investigated couplings, they are negligible in acoustically open or strongly vented designs and most critical when the coupling is occluding and the leakage path generated by the probe tube is short, as in power domes or specific earmold designs.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

5.1 Data Availability

Data underlying the study are available at Zenodo. URL will be inserted after acceptance.

Author Contributions

Conceptualization: FD, HH; Data curation: FD, LH; Formal analysis: FD; Funding acquisition: n.a.; Investigation: FD, LH; Methodology: FD, LH; Project administration: FD, HH; Resources: HH, FD; Software: FD, LH; Supervision: FD; Validation: FD; Visualization: FD; Writing – original draft: FD; Writing – review & editing: LH, HH

Ethics

All participants received hourly compensation and gave informed consent prior to participation in experiments. The methods were approved by the ethics committee of the Technische Hochschule Lübeck (vote 2020-09-11).

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